

Terpenoids: Part LXIII. Synthesis of *Trans*-Dihydrocarveol

O. P. VIG, A. K. SHARMA, JAGDISH CHANDER & BHAGAT RAM

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-14.

Received 29 May, 1971

The synthesis of *trans*-dihydrocarveol has been accomplished through an application of the Wittig reaction with methylene-triphenylphosphorane on *trans*-6-methyl-3-acetyl-1 (tetrahydro-2-pyranyloxy)cyclohexane and hydrolysis of the resulting product under mild conditions.

Dihydrocarveol, a monoterpenic alcohol, was first isolated by Schimmel and coworkers¹ in the oil of caraway and has been obtained since then from a number of essential oils²⁻⁵. On the basis of oxidative degradations⁶ as well as its preparations⁷ by the reduction of carvone and through the action of nitrous acid on dihydrocarvyl amine, constitution(I) was assigned for this alcohol.

Since dihydrocarveol (I) contains three asymmetric carbon atoms, it is theoretically capable of existing in eight optically active and four externally compensated modifications. Some of the stereoisomeric dihydrocarveols have been prepared⁸.

The present communication reports the synthesis of *trans*-dihydrocarveol through the projected sequence of reactions.

Hydroboration⁹ of 1-methyl-4(1',1'-ethylenedioxy ethyl) cyclohexene¹⁰ (II), the starting material, followed by oxidation with hydrogen peroxide, gave *trans*-6-methyl-3-(1',1'-ethylenedioxy ethyl) cyclohexanol (III) in 80% yield. Brown and Zweifel¹¹ have established that the hydroboration of monosubstituted cyclohexene involves *cis*-addition of boron-hydrogen bond followed by retention of configuration in the oxidation stage yielding cleanly stereochemically corresponding *trans*-ol. The hydroboration-oxidation of olefin (II) represents analogous situation and hence the incoming -OH group occupies *trans* position to methyl group in the molecule. The ketal (III) on deketalisation with hydrochloric acid in acetone solution, produced *trans*-6-methyl-3-acetyl-cyclohexanol (IV) which was treated with sodium ethoxide to fix the acetyl group in the axial position in this compound, if present, to the more stable equatorial one. The hydroxy group in the compound (V) was protected through the formation of its pyranyl ether (VI) *via* acid-catalysed addition to dihydropyran¹² in 93% yield. The ketone (VI) when subjected to Wittig reaction with methylenetriphenyl phosphorane, according to the conditions of Corey *et al.*¹³, furnished *trans*-6-methyl-3-isopropenyl-1 (tetrahydro-2-pyranyloxy) cyclohexane (VII), which was purified through chromatography over neutral alumina.

Finally, the ether (VII) on treatment with 10% hydrochloric acid in THF yielded *trans*-dihydrocarveol (I) in 85% yield.

The identity of the synthesised alcohol (I) was established through its IR spectrum.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Trans-6-methyl-3-(1',1'-ethylenedioxyethyl)cyclohexanol (III): A stirred suspension of powdered NaBH_4 (0.31 g.) in dry THF (45 ml.) at 0° under an atmosphere of nitrogen was treated with boron trifluoride-etherate (1.5 ml.) in dry THF (10 ml.) over a period of 5 min. After further 5 min., 1-methyl-4-(1',1'-ethylenedioxyethyl)cyclohexane (II, 4.5 g.) in THF (10 ml.) was added in slow stream and the mixture was stirred for 3.5 hr at room temperature. The reaction mixture was cooled to 0° and treated with sodium hydroxide (10%, 30 ml.) followed by hydrogen peroxide (30%, 30 ml.) and stirred for another hour. The product was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer washed with water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent and distillation under reduced pressure afforded 4.08 g. (83%) of *trans*-6-methyl-3-(1',1'-ethylenedioxyethyl)cyclohexanol (III), b.p. $130^\circ/8$ mm. (Found: C, 65.85; H, 9.99.

* Boiling points are uncorrected. Analysis by M/s B. N. Anand and L. K. Khullar, Microanalysts of our Department. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infracord with sodium chloride optics using thin liquid film.

$C_{11}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 66.00; H, 10.00%). I.R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 3450, 1100 cm^{-1} (-OH), 1050, 1030 cm^{-1} (a broad band, ketal). Other prominent peaks were at 2900, 1450, 1380, 1230, 940, 910 and 860 cm^{-1} .

Trans-6-methyl-3-acetyl-cyclohexanol (V): *Trans*-6-methyl-3(1',1'-ethylenedioxy ethyl) cyclohexanol (III), (3.0 g.) was dissolved in acetone (52 ml.) and mixed with aqueous hydrochloric acid (10%, 13 ml.). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 hrs. The solution was diluted with saturated brine solution and the product taken up in ether, dried and distilled under vacuum when 1.9 g. (83%) of the ketone (IV) was obtained; b.p. 124–28°/8 mm.

The above ketone (IV) was warmed with sodium ethoxide (sodium, 0.5 g. and absolute ethanol, 25 ml.) for 2 hr. After working up, it gave *trans*-6-methyl-3-acetyl-cyclohexanol (V), b.p. 124–7°/10 mm., η_D^{25} 1.4084. (Found: C, 69.00; H, 9.19. $C_9H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 69.23; H, 9.25%). IR spectrum showed prominent peaks at 3450, 1170 cm^{-1} (-OH), 1720 cm^{-1} (-C = O). Other peaks were at 2900, 1450, 1370 and 950 cm^{-1} .

Trans-6-methyl-3-acetyl-1(tetrahydro-2-pyranyloxy)cyclohexane (VI): A cooled mixture of *trans*-6-methyl-3-acetyl cyclohexanol (V, 1.2 g.) and dihydropyran (0.7 g.) was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.01 ml.) and the contents kept at 25° for 18 hrs. Thereafter, the product was extracted with ether, washed with N-potassium hydroxide, water and dried. Vacuum distillation gave 1068 g. (93%) of the pyranyl ether (VI), b.p. 99–102°/8 mm. (Found: C, 69.46; H, 9.75. $C_{14}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 70.00; H, 10.00%). IR spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1720, 1170, 1120, 1075, 1030, 960, 910, 866 and 815 cm^{-1} .

Trans-6-methyl-3-isopropenyl(tetrahydro-2-pyranyloxy) cyclohexane (VII): Methylene-triphenylphosphorane was prepared from methyl triphenylphosphonium iodide (3.36 g.) in DMSO (16 ml.), sodium hydride (0.4 g., 50%) in DMSO (8 ml.) under nitrogen atmosphere. To this was added the ketone (VI, 1.0 g.) in dry THF (5 ml.). The contents were stirred and warmed for 30 min. at 40° and left overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice and extracted with pet. ether (40–60°). The ether extract was dried, solvent removed and the residue chromatographed over alumina, when elution with pet. ether (40–60°) furnished the pyranyl ether (VI). This was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure to obtain 0.8 g. (84%) of *trans*-6-methyl-3-isopropenyl-(tetrahydro-2-pyranyloxy)cyclohexane (VII), b.p. 102–103°/8 mm. (Found: C, 75.56; H, 10.50. $C_{15}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 75.88; H, 10.91%). IR spectrum showed prominent peaks at 2900, 1650, 1450, 1370, 1250, 1200, 1180, 1120, 1070, 1030, 1010, 960, 910, 880 and 815 cm^{-1} .

Trans-3-isopropenyl-6-methyl cyclohexanol (I; *trans*-dihydrocarveol): A mixture of *trans*-6-methyl-3-isopropenyl-1 (tetrahydro-2-pyranyloxy) cyclohexane (VII, 1 g.), hydrochloric acid (10%, 10 ml.) and THF (15 ml.) was shaken at room temperature for 35 hrs. The product was extracted with ether. The combined extract was washed with dilute sodium hydrogen carbonate solution, water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent and distillation under reduced pressure gave 0.54 g. (85%) of *trans*-3-isopropenyl-6-methylcyclohexanol (I); b.p. 100–105°/7–8 mm., η_D^{25} 1.4787. (Found: C, 77.85; H, 11.65. $C_{10}H_{18}O$

requires C, 77.93; H, 11.68%). IR spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 3450, 1100 cm^{-1} (-OH), 1450, 1350 cm^{-1} (C-CH₃) and 1650, 890 cm^{-1} (methylene bond).

The authors (B.R. and J.C.) are greatly indebted to CSIR, New Delhi for the award of Senior Research Fellowships.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. Schimmel's Report, 1905, p. 20.
2. M. Rainer and W. Scora, *Amer. J. Bot.*, 1967, **54**, 446.
3. D. R. Dhingra, G. N. Gupta, G. Chander and V. M. Patwardhan, *Indian Perfumer*, 1957, **1**, 21.
4. A. G. Nikolaev, *Sovrem. Tr. Khim. Priv. Soedinkishinev Univ.*, 1966, **6**, 3.
5. Y. Fujita, *Koryo*, 1961, No. 61, 43.
6. O. Wallach, *Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 3984; F. Tieman and F. W. Semmler, *Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 2142.
7. O. Wallach, *Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 2142.
8. L. A. Tschugaev, *Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 2479; R. G. Johnston and J. Read, *loc. cit.*, H. Schmidt, *Ber.*, 1950, **83**, 193.
9. H. C. Brown and B. C. Suba Rao, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 5694; 1959, **81**, 6923, 6428; *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 1136.
10. O. P. Vig, K. L. Matta, Gurdeep Singh and I. Raj, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 581.
11. H. C. Brown and G. Zweifel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 2544.
12. G. Pattenden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, C-2385.
13. R. Greenwald, M. Chaykovsky and E. J. Corey, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1128.